

SPORT VA HARAKATLI O‘YINLARINI O‘QITISH METODIKASI

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Annation: Pedagogical thought was created and developed in ancient Greek, ancient Eastern and medieval theology and philosophy for many centuries. The development of pedagogy is inseparable from human history. The term "pedagogy" is derived from the Greek word, which literally means "the art of education". Until now, pedagogy has become a multidisciplinary science that works and develops in close connection with other sciences. Pedagogy is firmly based on philosophy, history and economics.

Key words: football, sport, training, competition, winning, exercise, hard work.

Until now, pedagogy has become a multidisciplinary science that works and develops in close connection with other sciences. Pedagogy is firmly based on philosophy, history and economics. It has effective connections with the fields of philosophy (epistemology, logic, psychology, ethics, aesthetics), biomedical sciences (genetics, anatomy, physiology, hygiene), a number of ergological sciences (design, ergonomics, etc.). The ideas of cybernetics - the science of optimal control of complex dynamic systems - enter pedagogy. Methods of mathematical and statistical development of experimental data using electronic computing techniques are used. It is known that any field of knowledge is formed as a science only if the object and subject of research are determined. The object of pedagogy is education as a conscious and purposeful process. The subject of pedagogy is the process of developing, teaching and educating people in the direction of the progressive interests of individual and community life. Education as a function of social life formed the subject of pedagogy, which emerged as a science of raising children. The purpose of the subject is to familiarize students with the features of teaching activities in the field of physical education and sports. Tasks of studying science: formation of basic skills in the analysis of pedagogical situations; is to develop self-awareness about one's capabilities and prospects for professional self-improvement in the implementation of educational activities. The

main problems of "Physical education and sports pedagogy" include such categories as education, upbringing, training, socialization, development, which can be considered as the main pedagogical processes.

Pedagogical process is a specially organized interaction between a pedagogue and students, formed over time and within the framework of a certain educational system, aimed at achieving a specified goal and aimed at changing the personal characteristics and qualities of students. effect. Pedagogical process - the main structural unit of the educational process; its uniqueness lies in the fact that it defines the system of pedagogical interaction between the educator and students: if the concept of "educational process" includes the whole set of purposeful formative influences on the individual, the concept of "pedagogical process" is deliberately reflects the established system. interactions.

Pedagogical process is carried out within a certain educational system. The system consists of: public education system as a whole, school, class, educational institution. 5 The main essence of the pedagogical process is to ensure the unity of education, upbringing and development, including the conditions, forms and methods of their implementation on the basis of integrity and teamwork. TEACHING is a specially organized, purposeful and controlled process of interaction between a teacher and a student for the purpose of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities (K.A.N.), forming a student's worldview, developing mental strength and potential, self-strengthening. educational abilities. KNOWLEDGE is a person's reflection of objective reality in the form of facts, ideas, concepts and laws of science. NEGOTIATION - readiness to consciously and independently perform practical and theoretical actions based on acquired knowledge, life experience and acquired skills. SKILLS are components of practical activity that are manifested in the performance of necessary actions and are perfected through repeated repetition. Teaching in the process of physical education provides one of its aspects - physical education, which is "the systematic development of rational ways of managing one's actions by a person, thus acquiring the necessary motor skills, skills and a fund of relevant knowledge in life lish" is understood. ” (L.P. Matveev, 1983) The effectiveness of the educational process, the duration of the transition from skill level to skill level depends

on the following: 1) motor skills and movement experience; 2) age of the student; 3) coordination complexity of motor movement; 4) professional skills of the teacher; 5) student level. motivation, consciousness, activity EDUCATION is a purposeful and organized process of personality formation. In pedagogy, the concept of "education" is used in a broad and narrow social sense, and in a broad and narrow pedagogical sense. EDUCATION (in a broad social sense) is the transfer of accumulated experience from the older generation to the younger. Experience means knowledge, skills, ways of thinking, moral, aesthetic and legal norms known to people - all the spiritual heritage of a person created in the process of historical development. EDUCATION (in a narrow social sense) is an influence directed by social institutions in order to form certain views, beliefs, moral values, political orientations in a person and prepare him for life.

EDUCATION (in a broad pedagogical sense) is a specially organized interaction between the team, pedagogues and students for the purpose of forming certain personal qualities that is carried out in educational institutions and covers the entire educational process. , purposeful and controlled process.

The main tasks of the pedagogical process: formation of motivation and experience in educational, cognitive and practical activities, assimilation of the foundations of scientific knowledge, value orientations and relationships; educational - formation of certain qualities, characteristics and relationships of a person; development is the formation and development of mental processes, characteristics and qualities of a person.

It includes normative, informational, methodological, personnel, material and technical, financial support. According to scientists and teachers, students' attitude towards themselves and others is determined by the concept of "Attitude". The concept of "PERSONAL QUALITY" is defined as a set of stable needs and usual methods of their implementation, which are formed in the process of collective activity and constitute the real object of pedagogical work.

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